

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF LESSONS AND PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: *The general innovation of the general pedagogical system is the process of coordinating its educational process - the most convenient of the many opportunities. It is possible to work in such a complex, dynamic, multifaceted, near-pedagogical system. There are alternatives, as well as targeted ways of organizing flow and educational activities. But only one of them may be right for the specific situation. Finding it is the main task of coordination. This task is solved by comparing possible alternatives and evaluating other available options.*

Keywords: *pedagogical system, theoretical and practical, coordination, blocking, innovation, process.*

First, it is necessary to determine which lessons are suitable for integration. The basis of such lessons is the closeness of the content and logical connections of the main topics of different disciplines.

Literacy classes (teaching reading and writing).

Integrated lessons An integrated course from the beginning is extracurricular reading. Here is the whole process:

- A) to improve the skills acquired in reading lessons as a book reader;
- B) work on the text;
- C) such as choosing a circle of interlocutors, choosing books.

Russian is also an integrated course that allows students to master the material of reading, writing, speaking, as well as the basics of algebra and geometry, labor education. In the didactic system, integration in interdisciplinary justification implies the compatibility of teacher (teaching) and student (learning) actions. Both activities have a common structure: goals, causes, content, tools, results, control. However, there is a difference in the content of teacher and student activities.

1. At the target stage, the teacher sets a general goal. Students, under the guidance of a teacher, need to understand the interdisciplinary connections, select the necessary knowledge from different subjects, in which they focus their

attention not only on the acquisition of general knowledge, but also on the transfer, analysis, should focus on the development of symptoms, abilities and interests.

2. At the proof stage, the teacher encourages students to generalize the concepts of different subjects to the knowledge that develops their worldview. Students will be interested in knowledge that expands their will, their worldview.

3. In the content phase of the activity, the teacher introduces new learning material, while integrating basic knowledge from other subjects at the level of integration evidence, concepts, problem sets. Students acquire a general understanding, problems at the level of general knowledge.

4. Textbooks, spreadsheets, new words, questionnaires, practical tasks. Students perform transfer, generalize, and attach characters using visual aids in solving integration problems.

5. The next step is the result. The teacher uses pedagogical knowledge to teach, develop, nurture, and integrate in order. The student generalizes in the system of knowledge and applies them in practice.

6. At the control stage, the teacher assesses, monitors and evaluates the readiness of students for interrelated subjects. Students control the assessment of their knowledge, both themselves and their ability to combine them across different subjects.

Coordination means the degree to which a pedagogical system is consistent with the goals for which it was established. The conformity achieved for one condition never conforms to other conditions. Therefore, the concept of coordination requires precision.

Coordination cannot be general, it can only occur with respect to a specified distance. It can only occur with respect to a specified distance. At the same time, it is necessary to have a clear idea of the purpose for which the pedagogical system should be coordinated, and which instructions should be consistent with the stated purpose.

It is necessary to distinguish between the theoretical and practical directions of coordination. A synonym for the concept of coordination is to theoretically calculate, estimate, compare, and contrast alternatives. Coordination is the introduction of innovations in the practical direction, reorganization, reorganization, making it the most convenient to solve the problems posed to it.

Criterion - despite the fact that measurement requires the logic of a single indicator, in pedagogy it always turns out to be complex, because the processes that take place in the pedagogical system can not be separated from the flow of

causes. As mentioned earlier, the desired results can be achieved through over-employment of teachers and students. The additional load leads to a decrease in working capacity, deterioration. Measurement criteria of coordination are needed. Only in this way can the teacher and students, working to the best of their ability, consider the learning process to be optimal without excessive workload.

It should be noted that according to the previous rules, no one has canceled them yet, in the first grade the child has to spend 1 hour to complete tasks, in the second year 1.5 hours, in the third - 4 hours in the fourth year.

Thus, the main criterion for the coordination of the educational process - as a measure, the two indicators are used in conjunction with each other.

1. Education - to achieve the highest possible results in the upbringing and development of students in those conditions.

2. Adhere to the established norms of time spent by students and teachers of all ages in the classroom on homework. The methodological basis of coordination is a systematic approach that requires the study of all components of the pedagogical process, the management of complex dynamic systems of mutual legal relations, based on a common theory. Consolidation by philosophical categories is based on "boundaries". The pedagogical system opposes the hyperbolization of one or another of the organizers in raising or lowering the pace of activity, the complexity of teaching, requiring the selection of boundaries according to their vision.

The main methodological requirements for the coordination of the pedagogical system are:

Coordination management procedures should cover the entire system.

Relying on the whole system of laws of the educational process in choosing the optimal alternative.

Regularly record the coordination capabilities of all system components.

Coordination is seen as a constantly evolving innovative process that supports higher issues and more advanced technology in solving them.

It should be noted that, on the one hand, coordination implies the adaptation of the pedagogical process to the existing conditions, on the other hand, it creates new conditions and requires the adaptation of the pedagogical process to it. There is no contradiction here, because these two processes continue in conjunction with each other. If we adapt to the situation today, it is due to a situation that does not depend on us.

But the educator always strives to coordinate them for success. In practice, coordination begins with linking the knowledge acquired by the classroom and

the school students in general, as well as the level of development of their upbringing, with established indicators. It is usually lower than the level of evaluation with a clearly defined indicator. After a while, the results are projected to the level of possibility of growth. A system of educational measures will then be applied to ensure the intended change. the forces expended on extracurricular activities are compared with those in the norm and a conclusion is drawn about the degree of coordination.

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